

EVALUATION AND SIMULATION ON THE MOLDING PROCESS OF CHOPPED CARBON FIBER TAPE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Randomly oriented strands Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (ROS CFRTP) have been the subject of numerous studies and industrial applications. The control of molding process of ROS CFRTP would prominently aid in the productivity of manufacture. This research aims to evaluate the compression molding outcome of a specific short fiber ROS CFRTP named as UT-CTT utilizing the analysis of charge ratio and thickness of free-edge samples and simulate the process with a new modeling technology implemented in LS-DYNA®, and eventually leads to a general prediction of mechanical properties based on the pre-set molding conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Applications of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have been gradually popularized in vehicle industries due to its high mechanical performance and great weight reduction potential. And compression molding is considered as one of the most efficient and reliable manufacturing methods to process CFRTP. In each CFRP manufacturing stage, from raw material to the final products, material cost only occupies about half of the total cost. Direct labor cost and utility cost shear the major part. Lean manufacturing and automation are effective approaches to reduce these costs. In addition, the molding conditions will eventually determine the mechanical properties of the compressed samples. [1] For mass production and capability to manufacture components with intricate features with lower costs, processing evaluation and fiber flow simulation are required.

In this study, one specific randomly oriented strands (ROS) CFRTP named as ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (UT-CTT) was selected as for its high fiber volume fraction, large fiber aspect ratio, superior formability and strong mechanical performance. [2] The UT-CTT samples were compressed with certain mass without a mold. The charge ratio of the processed specimens, which refers to the ratio of the compressed top surface area to the original top surface area. The charge ratio and thickness of compressed specimens were related with various compression time, molding temperature and pressure with exponential relationship observed.

Mechanical tests, such as three-point bending test, were conducted on samples and shown a clear degradation in the mechanical properties. Moreover, the free flow process of the sample was modeled by a new simulation technology for compression molding implemented in LS-DYNA®. The results showed that, with the charge ratio and thickness as a media, the mechanical properties of a free edge compressed sample, majorly the flexural strength and modulus could be approximately predicted by the pre-set molding conditions. And theoretical simulation accorded with the experiment results in predicting the charge ratio as well as the thickness of samples.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENT

2.1 Material

The UT-CTT used in this research was fabricated by air dispersion and stacked into the mold cavity to approach in-plane shear. It consists of randomly oriented unidirectional prepreg tapes (TR 50S, Mitsubishi Rayon Co., LTD.) and has a fiber volume fraction of approximately 50%, with

Polyamid-6 (PA6) as resin, provided by the Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. The UT here stands for ultra-thin. As compared to conventional CTT, of which the tape thickness is 130 μm , UT-CTT is just 44 μm in thickness, which tends to have less disorder in tape shape after compression. The tape length was cut as 19mm. These properties give it excellent mechanical performance and good flowability during compression molding.

UT-CTT (Ultra-Thin Chopped Carbon fiber Tape reinforced Thermoplastics)

Figure 1: UT-CTT Sample Fabrication and Molding

For the rectangle pile compression molding test, which will be explained in detail in the following chapters, the specimen was cut into 5cm*4cm in geometry with about 28 layers marked as intermediate material in the following figure 2. As mass was a critical factor to influence the charge ratio, it was controlled between 11.9g to 12.6g per sample. To measure the compressed charge ratio, thickness as well as other parameters, the compressed samples were put into densitometer. As PA6 absorbs water, the samples stayed less than 1 minute in water when measuring the volume.

To compare the mechanical properties between free-edge samples and common compressed components, reference plates were made as well. The size of a reference plate was 250mm*125mm with thickness of 2mm. As the reference plates had identical mass and were processed with mold, thickness is controllable. Each plate had mass around 92.5g. These reference plate would undergo the same molding condition as the free-edge samples while without the mold.

2.2 Experiments

The first phase of this research is to relate the charge ratio and thickness of specimens to the molding conditions. To realize that, the rectangle shape compression molding was conducted as present in the Figure 1, under 260°C and 240°C temperatures. The melting temperature of matrix PA6 is 220°C. As the molding temperature is higher than the melting point, thermal degradation of matrix would have unpredictable influence on the mechanical properties of specimen. Charge ratio, thickness as well as density of each sample were recorded. For compression time study, 1min, 3min, 5min and 8 min were selected. Every data point was contributed by three specimens. For compression pressure study, 2.5 MPa, 5 MPa, 7.5 MPa and 10 MPa were selected. Nonetheless, as samples would expand during compression, the pressures only refer to the initial pressure, which means the compression force stayed constant. Totally 14 molding conditions were considered. The top and bottom surfaces of compression machine were polished with sander paper and lubricated in advance to reduce friction. Five random points were taken on the plate to obtain an average thickness, yet most of them were located in the center area. The volume was measured by densitometer. For large samples which cannot be put into densitometer directly, they were halved by ultrasonic knife, which may lead to minor mass reduction. As PA6 absorbs water during measurement, the sample was placed in densitometer in a very

short period. Thus, a macroscopic charge ratio can be calculated, which is a result of neglecting the uneven edge area. This experiment has several limitations. The mass was fixed; therefore, the result may not be applied on other samples with different mass. Friction was ignored. Identical mass of every sample was unachievable. The operating temperature exceeded the melting temperature, which would cause unquantified thermal degradation. The edge area would be slightly oxidized due to open mold. These two phenomena shall have minor influence on the mechanical properties in that the compression time was short.

The second phase was to conduct the mechanical tests. The samples were first scanned by soft X-rays operated on the AccureX Lab device to discover the detailed thickness distribution on the compressed sample in micrometer precision, prior to any devastating experiments. Afterwards, they were cut into proper size in order to conduct the three-point bending test.

Figure 2: Three Point Bending Material Cutting Area

As for the 3-point bending tests, a universal testing machine (AUTOGRAPH AGX plus, Shimadzu Co.) was utilized. The span of supporters on the testing machine was determined by the thickness of the specimens with the span-to-thickness ratio of 16:1. Due to the tiny thickness of samples, the span was set as 22.4mm and width as 12.7mm. Five samples provided one data point. Stress and strain curves were generated to calculate the flexural strength and modulus. Note here the width of testing samples was shorter than the tape length. Therefore, the strength and modulus in reality are expected to be larger than the experimental results as the fiber length no longer keeps 19mm. However, here the ASTM Standards D790 was still applied in that the samples were too thin.

Ash tests were conducted right after the bending tests to check the volume fraction of samples. Due to the uneven thickness distribution of samples, the volume fraction was assumed to be different at the center area and the edge. Three pieces were taken from the center part, also marked as cutting area, as well as the edge part for all fourteen molding conditions. They were put into oven and burnt out at 500 °C for two hours for the resin to completely be vaporized. The volume fraction of each piece was then calculated based on the mass reduction measurement. Some unburnt samples were left for scanning to examine the internal structure in microscopic level and the fraction of void.

These experiments can only provide a macroscopic perspective to evaluate the quality of UT-CTT free-edge compressed sample. As present in the Figure 2, the edge and the center of the plate shall have large variance on thickness, density, volume fraction, strength and modulus. Further microscopic study is required to improve this research to be more precise.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Experimental Results

For the charge ratio experiment, the results present clear exponential tendency with compression time and contact force. Towards the tendency of thickness, exponential relationships were discovered as well. The advantages of high temperature are overwhelming. High temperature tends to give resin more flowability, which led to larger charge ratio and lower thickness under the same conditions. As mentioned earlier, the charge ratio was calculated based on the data of densitometer, the surface area was obtained when considering even thickness, which means the influence of edge area towards charge ratio was not in the consideration.

Figure 3: A. Charge Ratio – Contact Force Curve B. Charge Ratio – Compression Time Curve

Figure 4: A. Thickness – Contact Force Curve B. Thickness – Compression Force Curve

Figure 5 and 6 are the evaluation of density in the center and edge area towards contact force and compression time. Since edge area is not smooth and uneven in thickness, it is expected that density distribution is lower in the edge area compared to the center. Moreover, in contrast of 240°C samples,

the density of the 260°C samples appeared to be lower in the all two tests. It indicates there shall be more void in the 260°C samples. Thermal degradation of resin may contribute to this phenomenon. Low density was also observed in the edge area, where flow displacement is largest on the plate. The following figure 7 is a microscope inspect of a sheet molding sample and a free-edge sample. Based on the internal structure, free-edge samples have obviously more void due to its high flowability.

Figure 5: A. Density – Contact Force Curve in Center Area
 B. Density – Compression Time Curve in Center Area

Figure 6: A. Density – Contact Force Curve at 260°C
 B. Density – Compression Time Curve at 260°C

Another assumption was proposed. After compression, the volume fraction became lower than the fraction of raw UT-CTT material, which is about 50%. The later ash tests have proved this hypothesis. Overall volume fraction is from 45% to 48%. The reduction was caused by void and resin squeezed out. Figure 8 and 9 present volume fractions change according to compression time and force. Broadly speaking, the fractions do not have much variation. Yet in time study, the fraction in the center is inclined to rise during first contact. Potential reason is that resin is squeezed to the edge. Then the fraction drops back again due to the involving of air. This deduction needs further microscopic study to be firmly proved.

Figure 7: A. Scan Diagram of Sheet Molding Sample B. Scan Diagram of Free-edge Sample

Figure 8: A. Volume Fraction – Contact Force Curve at 260°C
B. Volume Fraction – Contact Force Curve at 260°C

Figure 9: Volume Fraction – Contact Force Curve in Center Area
B. Volume Fraction – Compression Time Curve in Center Area

In terms of soft x-ray scan results, the temperature seems to have low impact on the thickness distribution. Meanwhile, it was the compression time and pressure that majorly determined the outcomes. For time study, even a four-minutes period time gap could lead to a 200- μm thickness difference. The distribution tended to be more uniform under longer time and higher pressure. Center area have better and even thickness distribution than the edge. With these scanned results, thickness may prove to be a better simulation reference compared to charge ratio, as it shows detailed variation on the plate and edge area is also taken into consideration. The following is a typical results of soft x-ray thickness scan. Note here the color bar is scaling based on the average set thickness.

Figure 10: Example of Soft X-ray Scan

Figure 11: Stress-Strain Curve of a Free Flow Sample

Above is a typical stress-strain curve for the free-edge UT-CTT compressed sample, which was molded with 5MPa, 260 Celsius, and 1-minute condition. As the sample was melt without a mold, the tape shape was disordered. Mechanical property decline was expected. The three-point bending test was conducted to quantify the reduction compared with reference plate molded with boundary and provide experiment data for future simulation.

Figure 12: A. Flexural Strength – Contact Force Curve
B. Flexural Strength – Compression Time Curve

Figure 13: A. Flexural Modulus – Contact Force Curve
B. Flexural Modulus – Compression Time Curve

Contact Pressure (MPa)	Strength Reduction	Modulus Reduction
2.5	0.56%	21.61%
5	13.73%	14.63%
7.5	20.51%	24.85%
10	9.44%	10.52%

Table 1: Mechanical Properties Reduction with 260°C 3min Condition

Compression Time (min)	Strength Reduction	Modulus Reduction
1	7.64%	15.67%
3	13.73%	14.63%
5	20.81%	20.21%
8	-2.27%	10.17%

Table 2: Mechanical Properties Reduction with 260°C 5MPa Condition

3.2 Simulation

The flow process simulation is the third phase of this research. By applying the new simulation technology in LS-DYNA (a proprietary user-subroutine developed by JSOL Corporation), the process from layers of UT-CTT collapsing into fiber plate could be observed. [3] By obtaining the surface area and compressed thickness, charge ratio prediction can be achieved. Then relate these prediction outcomes with the results from mechanical tests. Theoretically, flexural strength and modulus can be foreseen with the pre-set molding conditions. Nonetheless, the limitation of this study is, due to its non-Newtonian fluid feature, out-of-plane movements of the fiber flow has to be ignored to simplify the simulation. Hereby, the flow mechanism of UT-CTT is introduced.

Figure 14: UT-CTT Flow Mechanism

The UT-CTT fiber flow in compression molding can be considered as a non-Newtonian fluid, which means the viscosity of fluid is a function of the shear rate which is related to molecular structures of materials. In brief of the mechanism of UT-CTT compression moulding, packing stress exists coming from the fiber structure in vertical direction. In horizontal direction, two types of squeeze flow exist, denoted as macroscopic squeeze flow and mesoscopic squeeze flow. Mesoscopic squeeze flow is the transverse squeeze flow of each tape. After compression, mesoscopic flow would cause dramatic change of tape shape. Macroscopic squeeze flow is a mixture of in-plane shear of tapes, out-of-plane shear of tapes, as well as misalignment of fibers. The demonstration is present as above. [4] For simplifying the model, only in-plane shear of tapes is considered in either experiments or simulation. The fibers are treated as straight and two-dimensional distributed. No sliding and no fiber reactions assumed. These are the critical assumptions to support this research as well as construct simulation model.

The new simulation technology utilized in this research simulates fibers into beam elements and model matrix with tetrahedron solid elements, with r-adaptive remeshing function based on an Element-Free-Galerkin (EFG) formulation. Relative motions of beams in the solid elements is simulated by coupling momentum along the normal direction of each beam element. [3]

Currently the modeling of simulation is still in process. The simulation focus is now laid on the reproduction of thickness distribution of the free edge compressed samples. The outcome of this stage shows similar tendency with the experimental results. Detailed simulation results and comparison towards the experiment data are expected to be present on the ICCM22 presentation.

CONCLUSIONS

A new compression molding evaluation system, designed for a ROS composite named UT-CTT, is introduced. The system is founded from the pre-set molding conditions, to an evaluation standard based on the compressed surface area ratio, noted as charge ratio, and thickness distribution study. Simulation model with a new technology implemented in LS-DYNA® are conducted with comparison to mechanical experiments, and eventually provide certain orientation to industrial applications based on flexural strength and modulus. To realize this system, further microscopic study and simulation on UT-CTT, and compression molding with various mass are necessary to be conducted to firmly support this research.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Lee, C. Bi, S. Tang, T. Hayashi, and J. Takahashi “Formability and flow front observation of carbon/polyamide 6 randomly oriented strand composites during compression molding.” *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 36(23), 1727-1744, 2017
- [2] Y. Wan, T. Ohori and J. Takahashi, *Mechanical properties and modeling of discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics*, ICCM20, 3222-4 Copenhagen, Denmark, 2015.
- [3] S. Hayashi “New Simulation Technology for Compression Molding of Long Fiber Reinforced Plastics: Application to Randomly-Oriented Strand Thermoplastic Composites” ECCM18 - 18th European Conference on Composite Materials, Athens, Greece, 24-28th June 2018
- [4] G. P. Picher-Martel, “Compression moulding of randomly-oriented strand thermoplastic composites: a study of the flow and deformation mechanisms”, *Doctoral thesis of McGill University*, 2015